

**Mechanism of Oxidation of Aromatic
Amine by *N*-Chloroacetanilide**

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ORGANIC *N*-halo compounds, particularly chloro and bromo derivatives have shown promising oxidising properties^{1,2}. The direction of polarity of the nitrogen-chlorine bond is also not free from

controversy. In view of scarcity of data on the reactivity of organic *N*-chloro compounds, we have studied interaction of some aromatic amines ($X-C_6H_4NH_2$; $X=H, 2-Me, 3-Me, 4-Me, 4-Br, 4-Cl, 4-COOH$) with *N*-chloroacetanilide in 1:1 ethanol-water (v/v) at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, the results of which presented here. These results further support our earlier view² on mechanism of oxidation of aromatic amine by *N*-chloroanilide.

N-Chloroacetanilide was prepared as per reported procedure². The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions. The first order rate constants (k_1) were obtained from the plots of $\log [a/(a-x)]$ vs time. However, after about of fifty percent completion of the reaction, the slope of the straight line showed a negative deviation (Fig. 1) indicating that the values of k_1 increase in the later part of the reaction due probably to autocatalysis. The second order rate constants (k_r),

Fig. 1. First order plot for the reaction of *N*-chloroacetanilide with aniline in ethanol-water (1:1, v/v) at 30° , [aniline]= 0.10 mol dm^{-3} , [*N*-chloroacetanilide]= $4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

obtained by dividing the values of k_1 in the initial stages of the reaction by [amine] were 25.4, 38.4, 24.6, 2.20, 3.00, 7.50 for aniline, *p*-methylaniline, *m*-methylaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-aminobenzoic acid respectively. The overall order of the reaction is two, first order with respect to each reactant. The results are reproducible within the limits of experimental error ($\pm 4\%$).

The oxidation of $ArNH_2$ by $C_6H_5N(Cl)COMe$ results in the formation of *trans*-azo compound depending on the structure of the amine. The products of the reaction of *N*-chloroacetanilide and $X-C_6H_4NH_2$ were *trans*- $X-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-X$ and acetanilide in each case. In no case any mixed azo compound was obtained. In a typical reaction, the reaction mixture (100 ml; $0.2 M$ aniline, $0.01 M$ *N*-chloroacetanilide) which turned reddish yellow with the progress of the reaction was extracted with ether after completion (90 min) of the reaction. The aqueous layer gave a positive test for

chloride ion. The ether extract on evaporation gave a reddish brown viscous mass which contained acetanilide as well. This was treated with dilute HCl and washed successively with hot water and ether to remove acetanilide. The coloured residue responded positively to azo group test. Electronic spectrum of an ethanolic solution of the sample was identical with that of *trans*-azobenzene³. The procedure was repeated in other cases.

A study on the effect of substituents has clarified the site of the reaction on the amine. As most of the anilines studied are *para*-substituted, the probable sites of nucleophilic activity are the amino-nitrogen itself and positions *ortho* to it. For the latter possibility, plots of $\log k_r$ vs σ_m (for *para*-substituents) and $\log k_r$ vs σ_p (for *meta*-substituents) should be linear. This was not so in practice. However, a plot (Fig. 2) of $\log k_r$ vs σ^n (normal substituent constants, free from direct resonance effect) was linear with a slope of $-3.3 (= \rho)$ indicating clearly that amino nitrogen itself is the effective nucleophilic site. Further, the reactions are facilitated by electron-donating substituents.

Fig. 2. Hammett plot for the reaction of *N*-chloroacetanilide with substituted anilines at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in ethanol-water (1:1, v/v) $\rho = -3.3$: (1) *p*-Me, (2) *m*-Me, (3) H, (4) *p*-COOH, (5) *p*-Cl and (6) *p*-Br.

The reactions were also carried out in different ethanol-water mixtures with ethanol content varying from 30 to 70% (v/v) (Table 1). An increase in the rate with increased dielectric constant of the media was observed indicating polar nature of the transition state. There was no effect of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction. Eyring and Amis relationships^{4,5} were obeyed, indicating thereby that the reactions occur by dipole-dipole interaction. As there was no effect of added acetanilide on the rate, the electrophilic species seems to be *N*-chloroacetanilide itself. Species generated by heterolysis or hydrolysis of the nitrogen chlorine bond are not involved.

The reaction rate remained unaltered when radical traps like allyl acetate or acrylamide was added. Apparently radical pathway is not involved.

TABLE I—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS^a FOR OXIDATION OF ANILINE^b AND *p*-TOLUIDINE^b BY *N*-CHLOROACETANILIDE^c IN VARIOUS ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 30±0.1°

	Ethanol % (v/v)				
	30	40	50	60	70
Aniline	6.1	4.2	2.5	1.8	1.0
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	7.4	4.8	3.8	2.3	1.5

^a $k_r \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. ^b[Amine]=0.1 mol dm⁻³.
^c[Substrate]=5×10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

The reactions were also carried out at five different temperatures. The isokinetic relationship was found to hold good. The isokinetic temperature (β) estimated from Exner plot⁶ was 348 K. The reactions are thus enthalpy-controlled. This is in agreement with the observed high negative value of entropy of activation.

The fact that only symmetrical *trans*-azobenzene or substituted products are obtained when *N*-chloroacetanilide reacts with aniline or substituted anilines, clearly suggests that both the phenyl rings in the azo compound are derived from amine only. When ring substituted *N*-chloroacetanilide was allowed to react with aniline, only *trans*-azobenzene and substituted acetanilide were obtained. It may, therefore, be assumed that under the circumstances cleavage of only the nitrogen-chlorine bond takes place. The rate-determining nucleophilic interaction of the amino nitrogen and the electrophilic chlorine of *N*-chloroacetanilide results in the formation of a cyclic transition state which then decomposes in a subsequent fast step to form acetanilide and *N*-chloroamine. The latter reacts with water to form *N*-phenylhydroxylamine and chloride ion. *N*-Phenylhydroxylamine is a stronger nucleophile due to alpha effect⁷ and reacts with another substrate molecule at a much faster rate to form *N*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine. The latter hydrolyses to nitrosobenzene. Nitrosobenzene and another molecule of amine react further to give *trans*-azo compound. Had nucleophilic attack occurred at nitrogen of the nitrogen-chlorine bond in the substrate molecule, a mixed azo compound would have resulted instead of a symmetrical one. Alternatively, a nucleophilic attack at the carbonyl carbon would have produced a substituted acetanilide with a substituted aniline instead acetanilide. These results clearly indicate that nucleophilic attack occurs on chlorine of the nitrogen-chlorine bond of the substrate molecule as reported earlier².

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